

ART STUDIES

ПІКТОГРАМИ ТА МІКРОТЕКСТУРНІ ЕФЕКТИ В ДИЗАЙНІ ВЕБ-ІНТЕРФЕЙСІВ: ІЄРАРХІЧНИЙ ПІДХІД ДО ВІЗУАЛЬНОЇ ТА ТАКТИЛЬНОЇ ВЗАЄМОДІЇ

Лукашук М.М.

*Київський національний університет культури і мистецтв,
кафедра дизайну і технологій, аспірант*

Зозуля Ю.О.

*Київський національний університет культури і мистецтв,
кафедра дизайну і технологій, аспірантка*

PICTOGRAPHS AND MICROTTEXTURAL EFFECTS IN WEB INTERFACE DESIGN: A HIERARCHICAL APPROACH TO VISUAL AND TACTILE INTERACTION

Lukashuk M.

*Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts,
Department of Design and Technologies, PhD Student*

Kyiv

Zozulia Y.

*Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts,
Department of Design and Technologies, PhD Student*

Kyiv

АНОТАЦІЯ

Мета статті. Запропонований у дослідженні підхід був спрямований на оптимізацію дизайну веб-інтерфейсів шляхом поєднання двох методологій: піктографічної комунікації та використання мікротекстурних ефектів у просторовій організації контенту. Робота зосереджувалася на розробці підходу, який дозволяє знизити когнітивне навантаження користувачів, мінімізувати залежність від текстових міток та покращити ефективність взаємодії з цифровими середовищами через застосування візуальних і тактильних сигналів. Основна увага приділяється заміні традиційних текстових елементів універсальними графічними символами, які завдяки семіотичним властивостям можуть передавати функціональні характеристики інтерфейсу без необхідності додаткових пояснень. Результати. Розроблено систему, що базується на пошаровій піктографічній організації, яка дозволяє створювати просторові ієрархії для покращення навігації та структурування контенту. Також було запропоновано концепцію мікротекстурних ефектів, що сприяють імітації тактильного зворотного зв'язку в цифрових середовищах, забезпечуючи підсвідому інтерпретацію важливості елементів. Наукова новизна. Впроваджена адаптивна система динамічних мікротекстур та піктографічних ієрархій, які дозволяють оптимізувати взаємодію користувачів із веб-інтерфейсами без перевантаження інформацією. Крім того, розроблена методологія сприяє створенню універсальних інтерфейсів, що мінімізують мовні бар'єри та можуть легко адаптуватися до різних контекстів використання. Висновки дослідження підтверджують ефективність поєднання візуальних та текстурних елементів у формуванні інтуїтивного цифрового середовища, що може бути застосоване в електронній комерції, соціальних мережах та професійних онлайн-платформах. Майбутні дослідження можуть бути зосереджені на розробці алгоритмічної адаптації піктографічних компонентів до користувацьких моделей поведінки, інтеграції запропонованого підходу у тривимірні та VR-інтерфейси, а також на аналізі впливу текстурних ефектів на когнітивне сприйняття веб-середовищ.

ABSTRACT

Objective of the article. The approach proposed in this study aims to optimize web interface design by combining two methodologies: pictographic communication and the use of microtexture effects in the spatial organization of content. The work focused on developing a method that reduces users' cognitive load, minimizes reliance on textual labels, and enhances interaction efficiency with digital environments through visual and tactile cues. The primary focus is on replacing traditional textual elements with universal graphic symbols that, due to their semiotic properties, can convey functional interface characteristics without requiring additional explanations. Results. A system based on layered pictographic organization was developed, allowing the creation of spatial hierarchies to improve navigation and content structuring. Additionally, the concept of microtexture effects was introduced, facilitating the simulation of tactile feedback in digital environments and enabling subconscious interpretation of element importance. Scientific novelty. An adaptive system of dynamic microtextures and pictographic hierarchies was implemented, optimizing user interaction with web interfaces without overloading them with information. Furthermore, the developed methodology contributes to the creation of universal interfaces that minimize language barriers and can be easily adapted to different usage contexts. Conclusions of the study confirms the effectiveness of combining visual and textural elements in forming an intuitive digital environment applicable

in e-commerce, social networks, and professional online platforms. Future research may focus on developing algorithmic adaptation of pictographic components to user behavior models, integrating the proposed approach into three-dimensional and VR interfaces, and analyzing the impact of textural effects on cognitive perception in web environments.

Ключові слова: семіотика інтерфейсів, когнітивне навантаження, графічна навігація, тактильна імітація, візуальна ієрархія, шорсткість поверхні.

Keywords: semiotics of interfaces, cognitive load, graphic navigation, tactile imitation, visual hierarchy, surface roughness.

Introduction and problem statement. In the context of modern development of digital technologies, web interface design plays a key role in shaping user interaction with systems and platforms. As the amount of information presented in the digital environment grows, there is a need to develop approaches that can optimize navigation, reduce cognitive load, and ensure effective integration of users into the web environment. Traditional methodologies for building interfaces often face problems of perception and adaptation, which can lead to difficulties in user experience. Of particular importance is the balance between functionality and aesthetic appeal, as excessive detail or, conversely, simplification can negatively affect the effectiveness of interaction. In addition, the versatility of web interfaces remains an important aspect, as they should take into account different styles of information perception, levels of technical training of users and specifics of their behavioral patterns. Thus, it is important to search for solutions that help improve the mechanisms for presenting information, organizing content, and optimizing interactive elements, ensuring a harmonious combination of functionality and intuitive clarity.

Nevertheless, the question arises of adapting visual elements in such a way that they not only fulfill an informative function but also contribute to an intuitive understanding of the navigation principles. The use of graphic components requires coordination with the cognitive peculiarities of perception, which is complicated by traditional approaches to web design. Another important issue is maintaining the relationship between form and function within the web environment, as excessive unification of interface elements can reduce their expressiveness and affect the effectiveness of perception. Additionally, the issue of tactile perception should be taken into account, which plays a significant role in the physical environment but remains less developed in the digital space.

Analysis of the latest research and publications.

The study [1] analyzes the mechanisms of graphic conventions formation, taking into account the role of visual similarity and communicative context in creating meaningful images. Using a communicative drawing task, participants developed strategies for transferring objects among similar distractors, which allowed them to explore the interaction between visual perception and social factors in the process of graphic encoding of information. Three experiments involving 138 participants (69 dyads) and an internal replication with an additional 130 participants confirmed that repeated interaction contributes to the creation of effective visual notations. The study showed that the effectiveness of communication increased with the number of object repetitions, which was accompanied by a reduction in

recognition time and the number of strokes in the drawings. Comparative analysis of the drawings confirmed that repeated images acquired stable features that better conveyed the identity of the object, and unique graphic conventions became less clear to external observers if they were not part of a common communication experience. An additional experiment with 223 participants (106 in the paired group, 117 in the mixed group) showed that the loss of the communicative context significantly reduced the accuracy of graphic symbol interpretation (paired: +15.8%, mixed: +5.6%). The analysis of drawings using a deep neural network (VGG – 19) revealed that the stability of images within dyads increased, while between different groups, drawings of the same object became less and less similar. The study also proved that the artists retained the most diagnostic features of the object, which was confirmed by analyzing masks from 443 annotations of drawings and 117 diagnosticity maps. In general, the results confirm that the understanding of images is based on both their visual similarity to real objects and the conventions formed in the process of social interaction.

The study [2] examines the role of semiotics and visual metaphor in web design, focusing on their application to improve user interaction with web interfaces. Two approaches to the development of web interfaces are analyzed: user-centered and design vision-based. The Peircean semiotic model of the sign is used to gain a deeper understanding of the functionality of web symbols. The classification of Lakoff and Johnson's metaphors (orientational, ontological, structural) is considered and a new division of visual metaphors into iconic and indexical is proposed. Iconic metaphors directly convey meaning through visual similarity, while indexical metaphors convey meaning through associative connection. The contextual and hybrid metaphors according to Forswill's classification used in web advertising are studied. The application of these types of metaphors to optimize web interfaces, increase the intuitiveness of navigation and the effectiveness of visual communications is proposed.

Study [3] analyzes the impact of visual elements of web design on user experience and the level of interaction with web interfaces. Particular attention is paid to the implementation of CSS, JavaScript, content management systems (CMS), and front-end frameworks.

The article discusses modern trends in web design, including the use of 3D graphics, animations, custom fonts, interactive elements, metaphorical visualization (iconic and index metaphors), as well as the impact of color, typography and layouts on the effectiveness of web interfaces. The importance of visual hierarchy, element arrangement and design adaptability in ensuring the usability of web resources is explored.

An approach to optimizing visual design is proposed, including the use of Progressive Web Apps (PWA), blockchain solutions to improve security, and artificial intelligence to personalize web content. Recommendations for web designers to integrate UX / UI principles that increase user engagement, reduce cognitive load, and improve the overall user experience have been developed. The study emphasizes the importance of visual design in shaping future web development standards and improving the efficiency of digital platforms.

In addition, it is worth noting the works of the following scholars: B. Wolf [4], J. Pelegrin [5] A. Shaikh, D. Koop, H. Alhoori, M. Sun [7], X. Chen, W. Zeng, Y. Lin, H. Al-manee, J. Roberts, R. Chang [8], A. Wasilewski [9], V. Sahai, P. Joshi, A. Sinha [10], J. Van der Meijden, G. Hooft [11] Q. Zhou, L. Ren, T. Zhang [12] and others.

However, taking into account the above-mentioned scientific documentation, the issue of developing accessible interactive web interfaces still remains insufficiently researched and requires further elaboration.

Objective. The aim of the work is to develop a methodology for interactivity of web interface design by combining the principles of iconography and microtexture effects.

Presentation of the main research material. The proposed approach outlined in this study is based on two paradigms, the first of which involves the partial replacement of traditional textual navigation mainly with elements of iconography and symbolic signs, while the second focuses on the introduction of microtexture variations and spatial hierarchies that implement user interactions in a more tangible way for users [4]. When these methodologies are combined, a unified principle of web interface design is created that prioritizes the clarity of interfaces, reduces cognitive load, and corresponds to the inherent human principles of perceiving the environment and interpreting visual and tactile signals. That is, the implementation of this methodology is related to the fact that design is most effective if it applies the idea of human behavior as opposed to focusing on the implementation of text-rich conventions or purely decorative aesthetics.

The essence of the first principle is pictographic communication, according to which pictures or symbols serve as long text labels or data representations. However, this approach is not limited to simply replacing single words with small images, but instead focuses on the use of semiotic properties of visual language, including curvature, angularity, and density of symbol shapes. Each of these properties has a semantic meaning that controls the user's perception on a subconscious level. By using images that display universally recognizable symbols, the need to constantly accompany interface elements with explanatory annotations that overload the interface with unnecessary information is removed, potentially saving space for functional interface details. Circle-shaped elements, for example, tend to signal continuity and smoothness of interaction, while the predominance of polygonal elements with sharp vertices may indicate a discrete

process at a particular moment of interaction with the interface. These shapes are repeated throughout the interface, zooming in and out depending on the hierarchical importance of the function. Over time, users will begin to associate these shapes with specific activities, or semantic features, such as research, or confirmation of new information, or social interaction.

Accompanying the described concept of visual language is the second principle, which focuses on the introduction of small variations in perceived texture – that is, microtexture effects, or resistive features. However, the digital environment of web interfaces does not allow for real tactile feedback in many traditional configurations, and its visual presentation is able to mimic certain aspects of physical tactile interaction with objects. Light shadow, gradient shifts, and visible surface roughness create the illusion of materiality, which generally determines how users interact with various interactive elements. When a button has a rough texture, it conveys a different sense of urgency and importance than one that looks perfectly smooth or «polished.» These variations should be used strategically so that the user can subconsciously distinguish which parts of the interface are more likely to be interacted with, i. e., those with which interaction will have more meaning; which parts of the interface will provide more detailed content; and which components serve as navigation guides [5]. This notion of simulated resistivity (resistance) is based on the observation that a person in the physical world mainly relies on tactile features when assessing the functionality of an object. Thus, the interface becomes a kind of simulation of this real tangible experience, using the habits and instincts that users have in everyday life in favor of simplified navigation.

The combined methodology is based on the concept of layered pictorial spatial organization, according to which images do not occupy a specific place in isolation from other components, but are instead arranged in hierarchical structures that emphasize the organization of content [6]. This visual hierarchy serves as a basis for managing attention, where primary images can be displayed at a slightly larger scale, or endowed with distinct microtexture effects to indicate that they represent major functions or sections of the web page. Secondary images, which are scaled somewhat smaller or positioned in close proximity to their primary counterparts, indicate subcategories or related additional functionality. Deeper layers of content can be represented by tertiary iconic elements organized in clusters around their main images, each of which should provide enough visual information to offer further familiarization without overwhelming the user during the first interaction. Thus, the lack of absolute reliance on textual explanations is a conscious choice motivated by the belief that images, textures, and spatial relationships are able to communicate information about most features in a more effective way. By focusing on the implementation of a variety of pictographic features, it is possible to partially remove language barriers by unifying the user experience regardless of the region of residence. In addition, the constant use of symbolic shapes and texture patterns allows interfaces to be updated without the

need to regularly introduce textual details. If new features need to be introduced, they can be implemented into the existing iconic ecosystem. Nevertheless, it should be borne in mind that the essence of this paradigm of building web interfaces does not deny the value of text as a structural element, providing for its positioning in traditional key places, such as headings, or in the form of additional forms of information that pop up only when a deeper explanation is absolutely necessary.

The concept of dynamic feedback through microtexture shifts and spatial reconfigurations is also a part of the proposed methodology. When the user performs an operation, for example, by clicking on an image or navigating to a new section of the interface, the visual texture of certain elements can be slightly transformed, signaling a change in the state of the system [7]. The surface of an element that was smooth may acquire small embossed protrusions or a diffuse glow, indicating that the system is processing information. Similarly, when a process is successfully completed, the texture may reverse itself to a smooth shape, or even acquire a more polished appearance with a light reflection effect, indicating that all steps have been completed properly [8].

In terms of practical application, this method can be implemented in the context of a large number of web environments, from e-commerce platforms to social media platforms. In the case of e-commerce, the main icons can represent broader product categories, where each icon will have visual features that correspond to the nature of the product category [9]. A soft and distorted symbol may indicate belonging to a category of items related to comfort or associated with household attributes. At the same time, more angular icons can symbolize, for example, electronic goods, the choice of which requires a rational approach. Nested beneath the respective primary icons, secondary icons can refer to specific products using a combination of smaller versions of the primary shapes, but with added microtexture features that somewhat facilitate easier distinction between subcategories of products. An icon with small stripes could represent an item that requires careful consideration, depending on the price parameters attached, while an icon with a polished shine could indicate an easier purchase decision. In general, the whole process of familiarizing oneself with the content of the web interface and selecting goods becomes more interactive, simulating the process of visiting a physical trading platform.

Given the specifics of social media platforms, the same system of hierarchy and haptic simulation can be used to improve the quality of user navigation between profiles, messages, and tools for interacting with the community. Large iconic landmarks at the highest level of the interface represent common social functions, such as sending messages, discovering content, or group interactions [10]. Each landmark is assigned a generalized symbolic identity that reflects its function, and when clicked, secondary visual layers are deployed through smooth transitions, revealing more specific functionality represented by icons organized around the central landmark. For example, within a collaborative

workspace web application, the landmark element representing the «Communication» department may be symbolized as a dialog bubble or a simplified conversation icon. Secondary icons can have small texture variations to communicate the nature of the function: a group block intended for informal discussions may have a softer, smoother visual surface, while for specialized ones it may take on a more structured appearance.

When it comes to the application of resistive design cues, the method itself can be adapted to fit the specialization of a particular platform. In high-risk transactional interfaces, for example, more pronounced resistive cues are useful in contexts where the user needs to be sure that they are performing a certain action consciously. An icon representing a specific important transaction may have a raised, tactile surface that instantly signals the need for increased attention. A progress bar can look like a series of abstract markers, where smooth, reflective icons indicate completed steps and textured, rough icons indicate incomplete actions. In addition, this concept is clearly aligned with the idea of adaptive color palette adjustment as the user explores the web interface deeper. Just as physical objects tend to change their visual properties, such as levels of wear and tear and color depending on how often they are used, so icons can change their appearance, adjusting their color saturation depending on how often the user interacts with them. However, in this study, this principle is implemented in the opposite direction. For example, an icon that is rarely visited by users remains in more neutral colors, signaling its lower importance within the ecosystem of a particular user, while icons that are frequently interacted with acquire more active color tones, visually emphasizing the importance of a certain area. As opposed to simply marking items as «favorite,» «already visited,» etc., color acts as a marker of priority and familiarity.

Conclusions. As a result of the study, a web interface design approach has been developed that combines the principles of pictorial communication, microtexture effects, and spatial hierarchy to optimize user experience. The proposed methodology is aimed at reducing cognitive load, increasing the intuitiveness of navigation, and creating a more organized structure of interface elements [11].

The use of semiotic properties of graphic symbols can reduce the need for textual explanations, making web interfaces more universal and accessible to users regardless of their language environment. The use of microtexture variations and visual imitation of tactile effects contributes to the formation of a sense of materiality in the digital environment, which improves orientation and perception of the importance of individual interface elements.

The developed system of spatial organization of content provides a logical structuring of functional modules, allowing users to more easily find the necessary information and perform targeted actions without excessive information overload. The proposed approach also creates the prerequisites for more flexible adaptation of interfaces without the need for frequent text updates, as the main changes can be implemented

through modification of graphic elements and their interrelationships.

Future research may focus on developing an adaptive pictorial communication system that takes into account the individual characteristics of the user and his or her navigation patterns to dynamically adjust the symbolic elements of the interface. In addition, an important area is the optimization of microtexture effects by integrating machine learning algorithms that will allow analyzing user interactions and adjusting the visual characteristics of elements in real time [12]. Research can also expand towards the use of spatial hierarchies in three-dimensional web environments, which will contribute to the development of intuitive management of complex information structures.

References

1. Hawkins, R. D., Sano, M., Goodman, N. D., & Fan, J. E. (2021). Visual resemblance and communicative context constrain the emergence of graphical conventions. *ArXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2109.13861>
2. Mirsarraf, M., & Ghaffarimiab, (2018). The role of semiotics and pictorial metaphor in web interface design. *International Journal of Arts*, 8(1), 20-24. DOI: 10.5923/j.arts.20180801.03
3. Thwiran, N. (2024). Analyzing the impact of visual elements in website design on user experience and interaction. *International Journal of Religion*, 5, 1608–1619. <https://doi.org/10.61707/gqm3j295>
4. Wolf, B. K. (2025). Guide to iconography design for enhancing U. X. *Your/UI Abilities – Uxcel Blog*. Retrieved from <https://uxcel.com/blog/beginners-guide-to-iconography> (accessed March 15, 2025).
5. Pelegrin, J. (2024). Navigation design: Almost everything you need to know. *Justinmind Blog*. Retrieved from <https://www.justinmind.com/blog/navigation-design-almost-everything-you-need-to-know/> (accessed March 15, 2025).
6. Spatial U. I./UX Design: A detailed overview. (2024). *Bootcamp – Bootcamp*. Retrieved from <https://medium.com/design-bootcamp/spatial-ui-ux-design-a-detailed-overview-428b8835fd94> (accessed March 15, 2025).
7. Shaikh, A. R., Koop, D., Alhoori, H., & Sun, M. (2022). Toward systematic design considerations of organizing multiple views. *ArXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2207.07558>
8. Chen, X., Zeng, W., Lin, Y., Al-manee, H. M., Roberts, J., & Chang, R. (2020). Composition and configuration patterns in multiple-view visualizations. *ArXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2007.15407>
9. Wasilewski, A. (2024). Functional framework for multivariant e-commerce user interfaces. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 19(1), 412–430. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jtaer19010022>
10. Sahai, V., Joshi, P., & Sinha, A. (2023). The analysis of animation & special effects in Indian advertising on social media platforms. *ShodhKosh Journal of Visual and Performing Arts*, 4(2), 754–765. <https://doi.org/10.29121/shodhkosh.v4.i2.2023.646>
11. Van der Meijden, J., & Hooft, G. (2020). Reducing cognitive load in multimodal interaction: Strategies for 3D design tools. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 36(3), 213–229. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2020.1787778>
12. Zhou, Q., Ren, L., & Zhang, T. (2018). The impact of AI on accessibility: Ensuring inclusive design for all. *Journal of Modern Computing*, 26(3), 341–358.